
Effect of Promotional Mix of Coca-Cola Company on Consumer Buying Behavior

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the influence of the promotional mix on consumer buying behavior specifically within the context of the Coca-Cola Company. The promotional mix, comprising advertising, sales promotion, public relations, and personal selling, plays a crucial role in shaping consumer perceptions and driving purchasing decisions. Through a structured research design, including surveys and data analysis, the study aims to identify the effectiveness of various promotional strategies employed by Coca-Cola and their impact on consumer preferences and buying patterns. The findings reveal significant correlations between promotional activities and consumer engagement, highlighting the importance of tailored marketing approaches in enhancing brand loyalty and sales performance. This research contributes to the understanding of consumer behavior in the beverage industry and provides actionable insights for marketers seeking to optimize their promotional strategies.

Key words: Promotional mix, Consumer purchasing behavior, Coca-Cola Company, Brand loyalty and Sales performance.

Introduction

The beverage industry, particularly the carbonated soft drink segment, is highly competitive, with major players like Coca-Cola and PepsiCo dominating the market. Coca-Cola has established a strong global presence through effective marketing strategies and a diverse product lineup, adapting to consumer trends towards healthier options. The company is recognized for its iconic brand and extensive distribution network. Coca-Cola continuously innovates its marketing tactics to maintain relevance and customer loyalty. Overall, the industry is characterized by rapid changes in consumer preferences and the need for brands to evolve accordingly.

In today's dynamic business landscape, understanding consumer purchasing behavior is essential for brand success. Among the key factors, the promotional mix stands out as a powerful tool to shape attitudes and drive demand. This mix includes advertising, sales promotion, personal selling, publicity, public relations, and direct marketing, creating a vital communication link between a business and its target audience. Advertising is crucial for building brand awareness and a positive image, leveraging various media to connect with customers' needs. Sales promotions offer immediate incentives, like coupons and discounts, to encourage quick purchases and create urgency among consumers.

Public relations aim to enhance a brand's credibility and reputation through media engagement and community involvement. Personal selling allows for tailored communication, addressing specific customer concerns during high-involvement purchase decisions. Meanwhile, direct marketing delivers personalized messages through channels like email and telemarketing, targeting specific audience segments effectively. Together, these elements of the promotional mix create a cohesive strategy that influences consumer decisions at different stages. By strategically applying this mix, businesses can attract customers and foster long-term loyalty in a competitive marketplace.

Review of literature

- **Razia Nagina, Jaskiran et.al (2024)**, The author has conducted the research on **investigating the perception and preference elements that affect consumers' decisions to buy carbonated beverages**” with an objective to identify the elements influencing the preference of consumers for the consumption of carbonated soft drinks. The study's information is collected through Secondary and primary data sources are combined Although secondary data collected from multiple sources enhances the research with broader industry insights and contextual knowledge, primary data gained through structured questionnaires guarantees direct input from the target audience. This study concludes that Coca-Cola is consumed more frequently than any other soft drink in almost the entire country. The ways that different cities' consumers consume soft drinks varied due to factors like flavor, availability, pricing, packaging, and advertisement.

- **Me Me Win Han (2019)**, in their study **Does promotion mix effect on usage of soft drinks in Thailand? Research on Coca-Cola Marketing mix in Thailand** with the goal to ascertain which elements of the Coca-Cola Company's marketing tactics have an impact on consumers' decisions to buy soft drinks. they have used descriptive research methodology and concluded that the target consumers for carbonated soft drinks are primarily aged 15-25, who are highly responsive to trend and advertising. Coca cola leverages brand trust, lifestyle connections, and advertisement spending boost consumer engagement and brand loyalty, contributing to increase in sales.
- **Adithya Deshpande (2020)** in his study **Influence of Strategic Branding in Soft Drink Market in Indian and Malaysian Context: Study on Coca Cola to remain Top of the Mind Brand (TOMB)** with a goal to look into how company observe the consumer behavior uses different techniques. They have newly obtained data i.e., questionnaire and concluded that customers do not see the Coca-Cola corporation's digital marketing efforts to be very effective and that the corporation needs to improve, especially in its aggressive approach. It also shows that strategic branding acts as a big part in Indian market.
- **Dr. Chandrashekar et.al (2021)**, The author has conducted a study “**Contemporary Marketing Strategies of Soft Drinks Segment and Its Influence on Purchasing Behavior in Prayagraj**” with a goal to know the impact of contemporary advertising methods on brand recognition. They have collected data from both first hand and second hand data sources and they concluded that the consumers' changing preference, coupled with sizing to improve affordability and product packaging has led to increase in sales of cold beverages in the country.
- **Ch. Prof. Franco Gatto et.al (2021)** in their study **Global Brands Connect with The Local Culture Advertising Strategies of Coca-Cola in China** with an objective to know how coca cola company's ads connect to Chinese culture and concluded that the vital connection between customer perception and culture in global markets, and the Coca-Cola Company's effective adaptation of Chinese cultural aspects.

Research Gap

The literature highlights a gap in analyzing Coca-Cola's integrated promotional mix and its impact on consumer behavior, as most studies focus on individual elements. It also overlooks regional differences and psychological factors influencing decisions. Your research fills these gaps by exploring the combined effects of promotional strategies in Bengaluru. It incorporates demographic factors like age and gender for a more nuanced understanding of consumer engagement.

Objectives of the study

1. To determine the consumer attitude towards promotional mix of the coca cola company.
2. To analyze the effectiveness of promotional mix of the coca cola company.

Research Methodology

This study uses descriptive research approach, a combination of primary and secondary data surveys are conducted with consumers of Coca-Cola Company in Bengaluru, to collect the first-hand information on their attitude towards promotional mix & how it influences their buying behavior, Secondary data was sourced from published reports, journals, and case studies to supplement the primary findings. Statistical tools **percentage analysis, Spearman's ranked correlation and chi square test** was employed to assess the research hypothesis. The data is collected from 120 Respondents in Bengaluru city via Non-random sampling using convenience sampling method.

Data Analysis

Table No 1

Table showing Satisfaction of respondents towards the promotional mix

Satisfaction level	No. of respondent's	Percentage of respondent
Very Satisfied	14	12%
Satisfied	38	32%
Neutral	54	45%
Dissatisfied	10	8%
Very Dissatisfied	4	3%
Total	120	100%

Analysis: The table above indicates that 45% of the responders feel neutral, 32% feel satisfied, 12% feel very satisfied, 8% feel dissatisfied and 3% of them feel very dissatisfied with the promotional mix of the Coca cola company.

Graph No 2

Graph showing Satisfaction of respondents towards the promotional mix

Interpretation

According to the graph, a considerable proportion of the responders are either satisfied or content with Coca-Cola's promotional mix, while the majority have a neutral opinion towards it. A smaller group voice their displeasure. This implies that a sizable segment is apathetic toward Coca-Cola's marketing initiatives, even though most of people are satisfied with them.

Table No 2

Table showing most influential among Promotional mix

Most influential Promotional mix	No. of respondent's	Percentage of respondent
Advertisement	54	45%
Sales promotion	26	22%
Personal selling	14	12%
Publicity	16	13%
Public relation	8	6%
Direct Marketing	2	2%
total	200	100%

Analysis: The table above indicates that 45% of the responders are affected by advertisement, 22% by sales promotion, 13% by publicity, 12% by personal selling, 6% by public relation and 2% of the respondents are getting influenced by direct marketing.

Graph No 2

Graph showing Most influential among Promotional mix

Interpretation

According to the data, Coca-Cola's advertising has a far better influence than any other element of their promotional mix. Direct-marketing, public-relations and personal selling have less of an impact than sales promotions, which also have some. This suggests that Coca-Cola advertising has a significant impact on how consumers view the brand.

Table No 3

Table showing Effectiveness of Promotional mix

Effectiveness of Promotional mix	No. of respondent's	Percentage of respondent
Very effective	10	8%
Effective	44	37%
Neutral	48	40%
Ineffective	10	8%
Very Ineffective	8	7%
Total	120	100%

Analysis: The above table shows that 40% of the respondents feel neutral, 37% feel effective, 8% feel very effective, 8% feel ineffective and 7% of the respondents feel the promotional mix of the coca cola company is very ineffective.

Graph No 3

Graph showing Effectiveness of Promotional mix

Interpretation

From the above graph, it can interpret as although many respondents are neutral, the data shows that a sizable majority of respondents think Coca Cola's promotional mix is effective or highly effective. It is deemed ineffective or extremely ineffective by a smaller group. This implies that even while some respondents find the advertising efforts to be beneficial, a sizable portion of respondents remain unconcerned about them.

Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis 1

H0- There is no significant association between frequency of exposure to Coca-Cola advertisement and the likelihood of purchasing coca cola products.

H1- There is a significant association between frequency of exposure to coca cola advertisement and the likelihood of purchasing coca cola products.

Chi square test

Chi-Square Tests

Value		df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	223.394a	16	<.001
Likelihood Ratio	203.468	16	<.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	95.177	1	<.001
N of Valid Cases	120		

Interpretation

The chi square test findings indicate that the p value is less than .001, which is below the level of significance of 0.05. Hence it is concluded that there is a significance association between the frequency of exposure to Coca-Cola advertisement and the likelihood of purchasing coca cola products.

Thus, Null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. It can be interpreted as there is a significance association between the frequency of exposure to Coca-Cola advertisement and the likelihood of purchasing coca cola products.

Hypothesis 2

H0- There is no significant strong relationship between the frequency of exposure to Coca-Cola publicity and the likelihood of purchasing coca cola products.

H1- There is a significant strong relationship between the frequency of exposure to coca cola publicity and the likelihood of purchasing coca cola products.

Spearman's Rank correlation

Interpretation**Correlations**

	How often do you come across publicity efforts related to coca cola		How likely are you to purchase coca cola products after seeing positive publicity about the brand
Spearman's rho	How often do you come across publicity efforts related to coca cola	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
	How likely are you to purchase coca cola products after seeing positive publicity about the brand	Sig. (2-tailed)	.923**
		N	. <.001
			120 120
	How likely are you to purchase coca cola products after seeing positive publicity about the brand	Correlation Coefficient	.923**
	How often do you come across publicity efforts related to coca cola	Sig. (2-tailed)	1.000
		N	<.001
			120 120

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The spearman's test results indicate that the p value is less than .001, which is less than 0.01 (LOS). Thus, Null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted, it can be interpreted as There is a significant strong relationship between the frequency of exposure to coca cola publicity and the likelihood of purchasing coca cola products.

Findings

The findings reveal that 45% of respondents feel neutral towards Coca-Cola's promotional mix, with 40% feeling similarly about its effectiveness. A Chi-square test shows a significant association between advertisement exposure and the likelihood of purchasing Coca-Cola products. Additionally, Spearman's rank correlation indicates a strong relationship between exposure to Coca-Cola publicity and purchase likelihood. This highlights the importance of frequent promotional exposure in influencing consumer behavior.

Suggestions

To improve consumer engagement, Coca-Cola can launch a feedback campaign using surveys or social media polls to gather insights on its promotional mix. Interactive content like quizzes or games can deepen brand connection, while emphasizing community and sustainability initiatives could enhance consumer perception. Personalizing marketing efforts through data analytics can tailor messages to specific segments, boosting relevance and reducing neutral responses.

Conclusion

Coca-Cola's promotional mix is well-received, particularly its captivating advertising and sales promotions, which enhance brand recall. Discounts and buy-one-get-one offers are significant incentives for purchases. Celebrity endorsements also positively influence consumer sentiments. Overall, the promotional mix effectively fosters brand loyalty.

Coca-Cola's promotional mix boosts consumer engagement and sales, with advertising directly impacting consumer behavior. Respondents noted being influenced by commercials and promotional offers. Utilizing various platforms, including social media and traditional media, enhances the effectiveness of campaigns. The flexibility of these initiatives helps Coca-Cola adapt to changing consumer preferences, maintaining its market share.

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